

Applications of IoT in Smart Grids Using Demand Respond for Minimizing On-peak Load

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Abstract

Increased on-peak loads requests have gotten quite possibly the most difficult issues addressed by numerous electric utilities and governments. Electricity power outages in developing nations are an everyday reality because of expanded economic activities. Consequently, traditional electric grids are being changed into smart grids (SGs) to address such issue of on-peak loads events. SGs enable "bi-directional" electricity and data flow between electric utilities and end-uses, and utilize different gadgets deployed at power plants, distribution centers and in customers' buildings for checking and control the grid functions. Consequently, a SG requires automation, tracking and connectivity of such gadgets. This is accomplished via the applications of Internet of Things (IoT). IoT supports different functions of SG frameworks through the generation, transmission and utilization of energy by deploying IoT gadgets (like sensors), just as by giving the

connectivity, computerization and tracking for such gadgets. In this paper, we present a comprehensive overview on IoT helped SG frameworks, which incorporates the current models, applications and models of SG - based IoT frameworks. This overview likewise features the roles of demand response (DR) programs and fog computing paradigm needed for SG-based IoT systems.

keywords: Internet of Things (IoT)- information & communication technology (ICT)- on-peak loads - peak loads reduction- smart grid (SG)- IoT in SG - demand response (DR)- fog computing (FC).

1- Introduction

The loads profiles in power systems are characterized with the on-peak load occurrences of the system (brief timeframes when a lot of electricity is demanded by consumers). The on-peak load events can happen at various occasions throughout the day, contingent upon the period of the year and the load usage whether by "residential", "business", or "industrial". Fulfilling electricity required particularly in on-peak events has an extensive issue to electric utility. as, this peak request is influenced on the planning of power systems as the structures of power transmission and dissemination should be intended to deliver the maximal requests on the electricity. For this reason, the electrical energy grid infrastructure possibly underutilized more often than not, arriving at its capacity limit at a little events of the year. Thusly, "commercial" and "industrial" consumers are charged with their complete energy utilization as well as their highest demand on electricity which dominates the power system development costs. The power charge can be separated in sub-segments like the generation cost, assessments, and expenses which address a little bit of the electricity consumptions bill of the clients. Likewise, industrial and commercial clients are keen on diminishing their consumptions costs, which are the main piece of the complete charges, without bringing down their electricity utilization. Besides, the electric grids address some different difficulties too, such as growing requests on electricity, unwavering quality, availability, arising sustainable power sources and maturing foundation issues and another some problems. To settle these difficulties, the SG worldview today is considered a favorable architecture that based on advanced technologies in areas of information and networking. These technologies would enhance the availability, effectiveness, quality, securing trends, support, soundness as well as versatility in the whole power grid system [1].

SG contrasts from conventional power grids in numerous perspectives. For example, SGs offer a "bi-directional communication" stream between electric utilities and end-users, but conventional power grids just offer "uni-directional communication" from the electric utilities to the end-users. SGs support Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), adaptation to internal failure, smart meters, unapproved utilization

recognition, and load adjusting, just as self-recuperating, i.e., discovery and recuperation from faults [2]. SG takes care of the issue of electricity wastage by producing electrical energy that intently meets the request on electricity. SG assists with settling on significant choices as per the request of energy, like constant valuing, self-mending, scheduling electricity utilization and streamlined electrical energy use. These facilities can fundamentally improve the electricity quality just as the effectiveness of the power system by keeping a harmony between electricity production and its use [3]. SG conveys different kinds of gadgets for checking, investigating and controlling the grids. these observing gadgets are conveyed at "power plants", "transmission lines", "transmission towers", "distribution centers" and end-users buildings, and their numbers add up to the many millions or even billions [4]. The existence of smart meters available at end-users' premises and the facilities of two-way correspondences are the fundamental specialized making way for "demand response" (DR) (Figure 1) technique that applied into "smart grid". DR is a promising innovation in "smart grid" to provide the always expanding on-peak loads through peak load shaving methods that is performed by service providers and clients to diminish the pressing factor on electrical power grid and reduce the consumptions bill costs of clients. As per the US Power Branch, DR alludes as "the services developed to enhance movements on electricity prices and offering different payments programs to encourage end-users to improve their consumptions" [5]. Basically, current studies typically talk about two DR classifications: "Cost perspective "and "incentive perspective "; every class has its advantages and exploit benefits of various directions of the potential for adaptable demand. Nonetheless, between different DR solutions and services, "real-time pricing" (RTP) has been viewed as the most productive and financial value procedure to decrease peak-to-average proportion of demand.

Figure 1: presentation of demand Response via two-directions flows of "power" and "information".

SG projects primary worry are the communications and monitoring for about greater than millions of devices that need conveyed monitoring via two-way digital interchanges. Thus, they would based significantly on appropriated mechanization offered by "Internet of Things" (IoT) innovation. IoT is characterized as

"millions of linked things acting with each other based on internet" [6]. Recently, IoT innovation is acquired extremely consideration within different solutions; in addition it took into account the "Internet" role in connecting different gadgets utilized in our everyday life. IoT is actual objects network associated with the Internet. These things would be furnished with implanted technologies to enable them to work probably within its network. The things in that network could process and work independently in a circulated, autonomous and pervasive way via advanced connectivity facilities. So, it is the actual requirement to establish the successful Smart Grids projects. Consequently, IoT innovation able to helping smart grids projects by offering different capacities for power system operations including the generation, transmission, distribution, saving and utilization by fusing IoT gadgets (like sensors and smart meters), in addition to allowing communications, computerization and controlling for these gadgets [7]. SGs are considered as perhaps the biggest IoT applications. Basically, all that utilizes power could be made more valuable by associating it to the Internet, (for example, microwaves and clothes washers which are associated with the Internet can be worked distantly and during off-peak events, along these lines saving expense, just as give individuals comfortable via automation). Subsequently later on, it would be imagine that the architecture based on the coordination between IoT and the intelligent grids will be huge than today, and this advanced and smart framework (like SG) won't be conceivable without the IoT innovation. Ordinarily, Secure, adaptable and consistently accessible bidirectional stream of continuous data is the substance of things to develop SG. Rather than depending on chronicled information, usage of ongoing data empowers electric utilities to more satisfactorily react to expanding and fluctuating of power utilization, change power streams to fulfill need, and consequently reduce on-peak loads occasions. Sending huge amounts of data from an immense number of heterogeneous smart gadgets to a distant and Cloud servers for additional investigation and analysis is a genuine problem and it requires time. Distributed applications, better depicting of SG, and requirement for quicker reaction infer that the Cloud-based SG situation is maybe not the most fitting. The likely solution for Cloud-related "bandwidth" and "latency" issues is found in "*Fog computing*" approach that is set up on nearby and distributed data processing facilities, subsequently altogether decreasing time and amounts of the transmitted data. Fog paradigm doesn't supplant the Cloud, it diminishes the time and amounts of the transmitted data by the Cloud by executing data processing near to where information are being delivered. So, just preprocessed data and results are being post to the Cloud for additional examination and lasting stockpiling that diminishes latency and resolve transmission capacity issues. *In this study*, we introduced a good survey about the application of smart grids-based IoT technology and the application of the demand response programs and fog computing needed for successful implementation of the smart grids-based IoT projects. From the applications perspective, few numbers of studies that talked about the SG-based IoT solutions were published. We interestingly summarized the state-of-art on the applications of IoT

supported both Smart Grids (section 8) and demand response programs (section 9). Also in section 10, we summarized the state-of-art of the fog computing needed for SG-based IoT.

2- On-Peak load problem

Within energy community the term “peak load” is used to describe one of the major challenges that have to be addressed by electrical utilities. The “Peak load” has been defined by many professions, experts, academics, and technicians in various studies, reports, and formal websites. According to [8], peak load is “an event where electricity is relied upon to be accommodated during consumption is fundamentally higher than normal production points.” Moreover, one of interesting definitions has been supported by “Low-Income Home Energy Assistance Program Clearinghouse” that described it as “the highest level of request on energy through specific time” [9]. Another effort introduced by The Energy Vortex that defined the “peak load” and its interchangeable term “peak consumption” as “the greatest amount of electricity to be generated during period where consumption at the greatest point.” [9]. In fact, on-peak load event would happen every day, every month, or every year. For electrical utilities, peak load may last for half-hour or hour that indicates the maximum demand of electricity consumption by end-users. In German or chine industry sector, the peak event happens in “day time”, while in Australia, it often causes in the “late afternoon” to “early evening time” (example: 4 pm to 8 pm) [8]. The occurrence of on- peak load depends on the “economy”, “weather”, “climate”, “demography”, the “day of the week” and other factors. During on-peak periods, the prices of electricity consumption is expensive than the prices of consumption at off-peak load periods. This differentiation in the consumption prices returns to, the electrical utilities need to exchange their generators with biggest ones or to involve other alternative generation resources to be able for supplying the requested electricity of on-peak events. The key reasons behind the occurrence of electricity shortage during on- peak time are: 1) the total amount of requested electricity is more than the maximum capacity of generated electricity, 2) Lacks of fuels needed for power generation that negatively impacts on the reliability of power supply. So, the utility have to balance between the power generation and the electricity consumption within the power system by applying advanced technologies and developing alternative systems like “renewable energy generation systems”.

3- The Smart grid (SG)

The Smart grid (SG), the comprehensive revolution in power grid also known as “intelligent grid”, “grid wise”, “EPRI’s Intelligrid”. SG is basically using information and communications technology for improving the conventional power grids in terms of availability, reliability, quality, efficiency and security. In other words, the SG is a term that integrates “information and communications technology” with the “traditional

power grids” for creating two-directions of communications inside each node of the power grid system using “advanced metering infrastructure (AMI)”. SGs allow electricity end-users to involve in power system to schedule their electricity consumption, this facility extensively improve overall power reliability and availability of the grids and typically reduce electricity consumptions especially during on-peak events. The smart grids development and implementation are typically response to the continuously advancements in various emerging technologies such as distributed electricity storages systems, computing power, renewable energy systems, and sophisticated communications. Today, high number of SGs projects is developed which applies advanced information and communication technologies in the grid applications, involving smart machines, devices and appliances of end-users level to build responsive and flexible power system. Moreover, these SGs projects applies advanced solutions, programs and services integrated with smart controlling, monitoring, connectivity, and self-healing technologies to: 1) enable end-users to take part in enhancing the whole power system processes, 2) provide end-users with interesting information that help them in schedule their electricity consumptions. Last but not least, SGs promise much great potential in various aspects such as improving power reliability, efficiency and quality, ability to establish and utilize renewable energy systems, ability to address many malicious attacks and enhance the security dimensions, decreasing in requested electricity during on-peak events, ease of repair adverse natural events and also decreasing transmission overcrowding expenses. In addition, SGs optimize the utilization of “Renewable Energy systems RESs” and “Demand-Side Management” methods through sending real-time data to control center unit, for balancing the production and usage at the consumers’ level.

4- Demand Response (DR)

Demand response has considered a critical part for advanced grids in which it enables electricity consumers to changing their patterns of consumptions to decrease their bills. On other words, DR is a set of services and programs that offer grid end-users the opportunity to involve in processes of grid system by decreasing or moving their needed loads during the occurrence of on-peak event. Ref [10] indicated that DR is the “services and methods for allowing consumers to change their usage patterns of electricity to avoid the consumptions during events of high electricity prices” [10]. Actually, the DR main objective is concentrated on making reductions in consumptions during on-peak occurrence. DR address on-peak load challenges through giving consumers chance to decrease their needed loads in which it resulted in mutual positive affects and financial benefits for the utility and consumers. There are various intelligent methods that enable consumers to be involved in smart grid demand response (or power system) like “Direct Load Control (DLC)” techniques that give the electrical utility the facilities to turn off smart machines and appliances

during on-peak load event. From functionality point of view, DR methods could be classified into three comprehensive groups as presented in **figure 2**:

- a) “Peak clipping” which aims to decrease on-peak demanded electricity to avoid the consumption to exceed the generation capacity. This method would reduce the end-users satisfaction and comfort as it limits portion of their requested loads.
- b) “Valley filling” aims to encourage the off-peak electricity consumption using electricity storage systems, like “storage facilities”.
- c) “Load shifting” aims to move the demanded electricity across the “time horizon”, like convert the consumption from “high-demand” to “low-demand” times, without any decreasing in total electricity consumption of the consumer over a day.

The electrical utility considers the DR programs as a significant and precious facility according to its great influence on power system in which they provide grid renovation efforts. In addition, they help in reducing the occurrences of peak load events, achieve more power grid availability; improve power translucence and efficiency, reduce CO₂ emissions.

Figure 2: The DR functionality

5- Communication systems

From power system point of view, the Communications systems architecture is the base needed to support the smart grids and its DR programs success, since the SG is based on the two-way communications system for improving power availability, reliability and avoiding electricity outage. This two-way communication facility enables the electrical utility and their consumers to involve effectively in the process of load management as; it provides smart monitoring for the available capacity of generated electricity during Demand Response event and allocating the required electricity. In general, the communication networks of smart grid system can categorized into three types as the following: a) Home Area Network (HAN) which links the smart appliances and machines in smart homes with the “communication gateway”. b) Neighborhood Area Network (NAN) that links a number of consumers inside a particular zone with the

center of electrical data. C) Wide Area Network (WAN) that links multiple NANs to the “Central Control Unit” as presented through **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: the smart grid communication infrastructure

The complication of these networks would lead to some difficulties during picking out a suitable networking connection cause various factors and capabilities have to consider based on the developed applications. As illustrated in **table 1**, different communication technologies which support the developed solutions of intelligent grids. One of recent pioneer ecosystem for ICT following revolution in mobile communications is the “IoT”. IoT is a paradigm which allows smart entities to be linked with each other via the internet for collecting and sharing data. Through the next sections, the IoT and its technologies as well as the possible and available IoT solutions supported smart grid and DR, would be discussed.

Table 1: networking Technologies for IoT_Smart Grid Applications

Technology	Protocol	Coverage Range	Application
Z-wave	Z-wave	Up to 30 m	HAN
Bluetooth	802.15.1	Up to 100 m	
Zigbee	802.15.4		
Wi-Fi	802.11x	Up to 50 km	HAN, NAN
WiMAX	802.16		HAN
Cellular	2G-4G		
Satellite	Satellite internet	Up to 100-6000 km	WAN

6-Internet of Things (IoT)

The information and communication technologies (ICT) world become more progression thanks to the recent revolution in sensing and networking technologies that link entities located everywhere. This connection and networking is called the “internet of things (IoT)”. Meantime the last few years, IoT has realized as Omniscient technology term. It visualizes a future as all digital objects able to be easily communicated together via adequate ICT to support the entire denomination of applications and services. According to [11], IoT can be defined as “a connectivity which able to link every smart things around us via internet to share and exchange data between each other for monitoring and managing these smart things”. Ref. [12], defined IoT as “a set of technologies subject to support efficient interaction and connection among huge various linked devices”. Moreover, [11] gives more detailed definition they defined it as “the organization of communicated advanced devices in which they supported with identifier in addition to abilities for sharing data with each other without any help of human”. Thus, via IoT paradigm may be almost objects surround us like “homes”, “intelligent grids”, as well as any entity (able to connect to internet) can integrate within IoT network. It is expected that this paradigm will connect 100 trillions of digital entities, and will extensively growth the Internet in terms of the size and scope. Typically, IoT concentrates on 3 elements namely “objects”, “Internet” and “semantic”. The “objects” that focus on intelligent and digital entities, things or devices can be engaged in IoT network like “RFID tags”, “sensors”, “cameras”, “GPS”...e.g. The “Internet” which defines the connectivity between huge numbers of smart entities using sophisticated communication technologies (like “ZigBee”...e.g.) that connect them to Internet. The semantic element that refers to a set of developed solutions supported within various smart entities.

As reported by certified many world statistics we suffer from nearly “seventy percentage of gas emissions” also our energy consumption is about “seventy five percentage of the total primary energy” every year. IoT undertakes to convert civil zones into “smart cities” using advanced information technologies for addressing these problems, improving living quality, and accomplish sustain targets. IoT systems enable real-time data collection, smart management for energy resources, streamline data collection for “traffic and parking” aspects, reducing gas usage and CO2 emissions. IOT projects provide comprehensive solutions for many applications that improve

resources efficiency, the quality of life and serve various areas and sectors in our daily life (as presented in **figure 4**) include: “smart building”, “Smart Grid”, “emergency services”, “security”, “industrial management”, and “E-health” [12].

Figure 4: IoT Infrastructure

These recent applications require to be supported with advanced, wide utilized and common internet protocols. For response to these requirements, many consultation and experts took a significant part in this mission and conduct a list of standard Internet protocols that have to be so suitable at each specific layer of the IoT network stack for enable the interpretation into various Internet solutions. **Figure 5** presents the main “IoT” and the “Internet” protocols.

Figure 5: Protocols of “Internet” & “IoT”

7- Integration of the IoT into a SG

Typically, the smart grids based on the communications networks that enable intelligent and real-time monitoring and control. These modern grids have the same IoT characteristics; include smart data analyzing and lightweight techniques. Via IoT paradigm, the electric utilities in addition to their consumers can usage an advanced communications networks (Advanced sensors and intelligent gateways). Recently, various IoT capabilities offered on SGs projects were enticed a great attentiveness within information technologies and energy areas that resulted in “Internet of Energy (IoE)”. Thus, the IoT paradigm has a grand part in the smart grid system architecture. The considerable motivation behind increasing number of developing smart grid projects is to employ automation in the power system as well as to improve designing, conservation, quality and functionality with ensuring that all elements within the grid system are able to “listen” and “talk” to each other. For example, in traditional grids, the utilities could be notified about any service disturbance when consumer tells them. But, in smart grids the electric utilities would be automatically notified about any service disturbance according to a specific element of the smart grid will send the collected data to the “control unit”. Thus, the IoT owns a great part in the previous scenario as each SG’s component has its “IP address” and able to support two-way communication. Actually, IoT provides real-time network communications to the end-users and smart entities/things via sophisticated connection technologies. As well as, it provides the facilities and functions needed for recognizing fast and continuous delivery of data through different facilities which enable the SG to enhance its efficiency. The IoT applications supported smart grid functionality can be categorized into three classes according to the three basic layers of IoT build: Firstly, IoT application for realizing various smart objects linked within IoT network, for monitoring and controlling their status i.e., at “the perception layer of IoT”. Secondly, IoT application for collecting data from smart objects using advanced networking technologies i.e., at “the network layer of IoT”. Thirdly, IoT applications propose for smart monitoring and controlling of the SG operations using various applications i.e., at “the application layer of IoT”.

8- The IOT Applications in Smart Grid

There is a wide list of expected IoT applications that can aid SG operations some of these expected application have been exactly implemented, as shown in **Figure 6. Table 2** summarized the state-of-art on the applications of IoT supported Smart Grid. In the following, we present and explain the proposed IoT applications in SG introduced in the studies [13]–[39].

Figure 6: IoT applications in smart grid

Table 2: survey of the proposed IoT applications in smart grid

References	Smart Grid Area	Applications
[13]–[14]- [15]- [16]- [17]- [18]	Power Consumption	“Smart Home”
[19]	Power Consumption	“Information Management Systems for EVs”
[20]	Power Transmission	“Transmission Tower Protection”
[21] – [22] –[23]- [24] - [25]	Power Transmission	“Monitoring of Power Transmission Lines”
[26], [27], [28]- [29] - [30] - [31]	Power Consumption	“Renewable Energy Resources”
[32]–[33]- [34]- [35]- [36]	Power Consumption	“Power Demand Management”
[37]- [38]- [39]	Power Consumption	“Advanced Metering Infrastructure”

IoT application in Smart home: IoT technology has a key role in the smart grid by grasping smart machines, and appliances of smart homes and buildings. The smart home enable smart environmental monitoring through sensor and actuator nodes in which they send the oversight data for the “control unit” inside home [26]. The “control unit” allows individuals for controlling as well as monitoring their smart devices and appliances from anyplace at anytime. This unit also usages the data collected from various smart machines and appliances in order to reveal any critical event then convey individuals or consumers to take suitable actions. These facilities would only be recognized as a result of employing IoT technology. So, the smart home is considered one of a main portion of the SG for recognizing ongoing interconnection between consumers and the electric utility which improve the grid serving quality, enhance the power reliability, and to supply customers’ electricity demands in the most appropriate possible ways.

Information Management System-aided Electric Vehicle: EV is an eco-accommodating transportation facility aims to decreasing “carbon dioxide emissions” [19]. The EV charging framework is made out of a power supply system, charging gear and monitoring system. The power supply part where liable for the yield and the executives of power. The chargeable part “charges/discharges” the vehicles. The checking system is liable for ongoing observing of the charging system as well as security aspects. IoT takes a critical role within that monitoring system, as it offering data management capabilities that incorporate various elements within the chargeable part [19]. The GPS based IoT supported in **E-Vehicle** would assist driver in many purposes like finding the closest gas station in addition to sending the traffic data.

Advanced Metering Framework (AMI): Customarily, power utilization data was gathered physically on location at explicit time stretches. This event definitely prompted deficiencies regarding precision and idealness. “AMI meter” or “Smart Meter” is a progressed and computerized variant of the customary electric meters that is implemented external the home. An AMI framework is quite possibly the main elements of the Smart Grids, gathering the constant power utilization information with high dependability, preparing this data and henceforth giving continuous checking, measurements and power utilization investigation. Other than estimating the power utilization, AMI meters likewise send electricity and pricing data from service organizations to the end-users, along these lines permitting two way interchanges, on account of the IoT. By utilizing

this framework, IoT innovation could assist the end-users with setting aside cash by changing their power utilization patterns depended on the investigation of their electricity utilization.

Integration of Renewable Energy Resources (RERs): Renewable energy systems are dynamically incorporated into the present electric grid. Over last few years, many experts and academics give in impressive consideration in smart grid concentrates because of environment changes and natural pressing factors. Sustainable energy emphatically affects the worldwide climate by producing power without fossil fuel byproducts [27]. The main features of renewable energy sources in terms of generation patterns, they are irregular and depend on climate, area and environment, so they present critical difficulties for the predictability and availability of the demanded energy. Such issues are tended to utilizing the consistent interoperability and availability given by the IoT innovation. Besides, the IoT innovation utilizes advanced sensors to gather ongoing climate data that helps in estimating energy availability soon.

Management of Power demand: otherwise called “demand-side energy management”, is characterized as the adjustment in the power utilization patterns of end-users according to the moving in energy consumption costs by electric utility [40]. This activity is utilized to limit the customer's electricity bill, diminish the operational expense of the grid and energy misfortunes, in addition to minimize the requested load during on-peak events [41]. IoT gadgets gather the electricity consumption data of different home apparatuses and send them to the “home control units”. Hence, the SG control unit plans the electricity utilization of home apparatuses dependent on the customers' characterized inclinations so that every customer's electricity bill is reduced.

Online Power Transmission Monitoring: is perhaps the main employment of the IoT in the SG, explicitly for debacle anticipation and relief. Sensors would now be able to be utilized to accomplish continuous “electronic control for electricity transmission”. This recent electronic control framework involved the following parts: 1) the sensors that composited on the electricity transmission paths between transmission pinnacles for monitoring the status of transmission paths. 2) the subsequent part has sensors composited on the transmission pinnacles for monitoring their status and their ecological boundaries. IoT empowers the connection across the electricity transmission paths sensors and the transmission pinnacles sensors.

Transmission Pinnacle Assurance: it is a basic element of power transmission, created to upgrade the wellbeing of transmission towers from actual harm by ravaging of parts, catastrophic events, perilous development and developing trees under the establishments. With the assistance of WSNs, IoT innovation can enable distant observing for tending these security dangers. The IoT-aided transmission tower assurance framework includes different sensors that produce early alerts of dangers to high voltage transmission towers, empowering speedy reactions. The sensors incorporate vibration sensors, anti-theft bolts, an inclining sensor and a camcorder. These sensors and the sink hub structure a WSN. The sensors identify any danger, and impart the pertinent signs to the sink hub. The sink hub gets these signs from the sensors, processing them to get information and sends the information to the control unit.

9- The Applications of IoT-aided DR the integration of IoT and DR enables the consumers and electric utility to oversee electricity utilization by checking electricity use and changing utilization patterns for limiting cost and energy consumptions [42]. The critical features of DR are the improvement of ICT, in addition to the necessary connections and checking that help the DR procedures, for example, climbing to utilize the advanced metering foundation and IoT. Moreover, the IoT applications in DR got more consideration than the conventional applications of energy observing and control. In any case, the IoT application in DR of the existing studies primarily centered on in-home power management, as shown in **table 3**. But, less interest was considered to DR systems, which was produced depended on IoT for the utilization of electric consumers.

Table 3: Survey of the proposed IoT applications in DR

References	Network	Protocols	Main objective
[43]	HAN, WAN	IoT stack protocols	Propose WBFA algorithm to reduce “on-peak-to-average ratio”.
[44]			Develop a system to manage the linked smart devices within SG.
[45]			Propose a real time DR platform in intelligent grids.
[46]			Develop a framework for balancing load using IoT.
[47]			Establish extensive framework for managing load.
[48]	HAN		Integrate web service solutions with the smart meter for minimize load consumption.
[49]	HAN, NAN	Internet stack protocols	Multiple web services enabled devices offer metering data on an event based mode.
[50]	HAN, WAN	IoT stack protocols	Load management system to address peak events through adjusting pricing rate and managing load demand.
[51]		Internet stack protocols	Managing Load system to monitor home appliances and collect their consumption data and send notifications for the electric end-users on Twitter.
[52]	HAM		DR solution for controlling air conditioners based on online control feature.

Ghulam H. et al. [43], they proposed WBFA algorithm to methodically deal with the electricity management via utilization of IoT-empowered individuals to schedule their smart machines to reduce “on-peak events”, limit power consumption price, and augment consumers comfort (CC). The WBFA-based system consequently reacts to cost based DR services to address the serious issue of the DR programs, which is the limit of consumer's information to react after getting DR prices signals. They reported that their developed system beats the existing techniques in market regarding execution measurements.

Ashish K. et al. [44], they propose a monitor system for managing the linked smart apparatuses within a smart grid. This system is likewise equipped for arranging the network progressively. They evaluate the latency execution for their platform utilizing the suitably Orange communication network. It is seen that NB-IoT empowered smart gadgets could be controlled and checked with a

most extreme latency less than “8 seconds” in the “deep-indoor environment” and 2 seconds for the “outdoor environment”.

Luca B. et al. [45], they introduced a novel disseminated structure for on-going administration of DR in intelligent grid. Their structure allows a “close” real time co- simulation module to approve new DR-strategies using IoT technology to perform programming-in-the-loop. Thus, the conduct of true real-world power frameworks can be imitated in a sensible manner and diverse DR-approaches can be effectively implemented and potentially supplanted in a “plug and-play design”, without influencing the remainder of the structure. Also, this solution incorporates IoT associated smart gadgets at consumer level and along the Smart Grid to recover power data and send activation orders. In this way, the system is likewise prepared to oversee DR in a genuine Smart Grid. This is shown on a reasonable Smart Grid with an experiment DR-strategy.

Jacobsen and Mikkelsen [46], designed the framework project 7 (FP7), the European-subsidized scheme for smart power system, named “SmarHG”. The point of this venture is to assist end-users and the electric service provider to organize power utilization through IoT modules. The framework utilized open source conventions, for example, “smart energy profile 2 (SEP2)”, and “ZigBee IP”. This framework initially began in 2012 and ran through a 3 year time frame and spending about 4.5 million EUR.

Kelly et al. [47] represented a successful minimal cost and adaptable solution for home power management. The vital elements of the proposed model are the inconspicuous checking of homegrown uses, which give encompassing intelligence to diminishing the electricity utilization based on IoT innovation. The aftereffect of the developed solution displayed roughly 97% accuracy in detecting data transmission.

Altmann et al. [48] they structured a varied meter network to find a solution for the multi-seller problems. An Online smart metering platform was implemented utilizing a “device profile for web services (DPWS)” and brilliant message language. This platform is registered to any IP-based actual technology. To lessen the correspondence overhead, they utilized a CoAP convention rather than HTTP, and EXI was utilized rather than XML paired encoding. Consequently, the traffic overhead was decreased by more than ninety percentages. The recommended method could be applied in the DR module for checking the electricity utilization.

Karnouskos et al. [49] created practical intelligent metering in an event based framework. A multi-specialist framework and online services of the DPWS convention were utilized to gauge and assess a few gadget attributes. This methodology performs exact metering estimation for DR applications. As indicated by this arrangement, a solitary gadget can send its metering data to wide numbers of intelligent meters which were bought in. This framework enables detection for the new metering gadget automatically. A synchronization technique was applied for processing millions of smart meters for the genuine smart meter unit.

Ali et al. [50] developed a pricing strategy model using the Demand Response services supported by IoT. As indicated by the costs declared from the supplier, their model would control the consumers' apparatuses distantly when the peak events occurred. Consumers adjust their electricity utilization as indicated by the prices signs to boost their own advantages.

Lloret et al. [51] built up a minimal cost in-home power management framework. As indicated by this framework, the consumer incorporates the timetable of apparatuses and the ordinary activity (healthy statue) of every machine. At whatever time, an up- normal event is revealed on the “gateway”, the framework will notify the consumer through its account on Twitter. Besides, every consumer would be able to plan his/her timetable of the machines distantly.

Wu et al. [52] created the Demand Response framework that diminish the on-peak periods and limit electricity bills. The outcomes demonstrated that their framework would enable remote control for electricity consumption which will help in reduce the request on electricity and the outflow of carbon dioxide every year.

10- Cloud and Fog Computing for IoT-Aided SG Systems

Smart grid utilizes smart meters that able to gather and convey power utilization data as well as private individuals' data, for example, electricity consumptions data at gadget level and so on. The continuously advancement of power frameworks requires the intelligent grids to encourage constant management and checking of all power system operations thanks to two-paths of data and power offered by these intelligent grids. Smart meters generate high data quantities which need to extensive capabilities for processing and storing it. Thus, the “Cloud computing (CC)” is the best

choices in this case as it provides sophisticated facilities to perform these tasks. “Cloud computing” gives flexible assets and administrations partook in “communication network”, “parallel processing”, as well as “omnipresent access”. In CC distant shared resources and information are given to end-users who demand them. It offers three models to allow access to the shared “computing resources”. The cloud computing frameworks own outstanding abilities that enable exchanging information in or out these frameworks. Because of these abilities, cloud computing takes great interest in the power field. Firstly, power industry endeavors to create environmentally friendly power energy to forestall an Earth-wide temperature boost. Cloud computing is the ideal possibility to accomplish effective and efficient green energy delivering. Venture and operational expense is another explanation, as CC runs on inexpensive data centers. **Figure 7** portrays CC technology within the intelligent grid where the end-users’ as well as the electric utility are connected to the cloud.

Figure 7: Cloud computing in smart grid

Despite the fact that the CC model is considered a proficient for intelligent grids, it neglects to ensure the “Quality-of-Experience (QoE)” necessities for the grids administrations, inactivity, transmission capacity, energy utilization, and communication cost. These challenges can undoubtedly be tended by “fog computing”. It is an exceptionally virtualized paradigm that stretches out the cloud computing to the edge of the network so that “computation”, “storage” and “networking services” can be locally conducted. In this manner, “fog Computing” is an environment that offers a spot for gathering, analyzing, putting away data received from smart meter prior to sending them to cloud, as demonstrated in **Figure 8**. This platform performs as an extension between smart grid and cloud. It is topographically allocated and redesigns cloud

computing through extra abilities including diminished latency, expanded security and locality for smart grids.

Figure 8: Proposed fog computing model in smart grid

Hussain M. et al. [53] they develop a mathematical framework for a regular fog based SG model that clarifies the Planning and Arrangement of fog computing in SG (PPFG). Essentially, the proposed PPFG system is an “Integer Linear Programming (ILP)” problem that decides the ideal area, the limit and the quantity of Fog Computing Hubs (FCH) for limiting the whole network deferral and energy utilization of network components. our proposed model has been running on a little network of “30 Electric Vehicles (EV)”, “10 FCHs “and “one cloud server”, they clarified the processing of PPFG. Truth be told, the authors executed a total investigation that resulted in more readily comprehend the working of every constraint in the PPFG model. The “NSGA-II algorithm” performance was additionally compared with the outcomes got by the conventional ILP solver.

Saman Z. et al. [54] developed the cloud/fog framework to asset the whole operation of smart grids. Their vital thought about this framework is to decide a leveled design of cloud and fog facilities to give various services for SG asset processes. As to execution improvement of cloud computing, distinctive load adjusting procedures are utilized. For load adjusting between a SG “client's solicitations” and “service providers”, five techniques were actualized. Additionally, they developed a mixture method called “hybrid artificial bee ant colony optimization (HABACO)”. The findings of their Simulation reported that the HABACO method outperformed other algorithms.

Forcan M. et al. [55] this paper centers on the development of communication framework models to be utilized for voltage profile observing and power misfortunes assessment in SG. A notable “IEEE

13 feeder power framework network model” is utilized for simulation investigation of proposed communication platforms and later acquired outcomes uncovered their preferences and disadvantages. The “Cloud- Fog based methodology” has shown a generous decrease of absolute simulation time and data amounts being shipped off the Cloud. Along these lines, the favorable circumstance that fog processing layer integrated with SG monitoring is approved. The proposed communication structures can be effortlessly altered and adjusted to provide smart monitoring in SG with different geographies and directions.

Rabindra K. et al. [56] in this investigation, the use of fog computing for a “microgrid” framework is proposed, mentioned and assessed. The design of the fog and cloud computing are thought about. It has been discovered that the fog level goes about as an auxiliary layer to cloud computing where the data can be put away and recovered momentarily and allow the smart meters operate autonomously. The outcomes acquired illustrate the adequacy of Fog computing for smart grid architecture regarding reduced power consumption, decreased storage necessity and overlay examination abilities. The principle task is to instruct the energy research staff to overhaul such progressive constructions for execution.

Huang Y. et al. [57] designed an edge computing system for ongoing observing, that moves the computation away from the incorporated cloud to be close to gadget edge servers. To amplify the advantages, they form an extensive schedule for additionally improve the system as well as develop a productive technique depended on the strengthening methodology. According to the presented outputs, their suggested system would decrease latency eighty five percentage contrasting with the cloud arrangement.

Hussain M. et al. [58] they at that point implement an expense advancement model for FC that mutually explores data of customer affiliation, burden allocation, virtual machine position requirements. After testing their implemented model they found out the general delay in service in case of fog computing was extremely less than the delay in case of cloud worldview. They additionally realized that the Fog Computing brings down the energy utilization of the cloud computing paradigm by over forty four percentage.

Javed A. et al. [59] they researched the reconciliation of organizing local electricity that needs cloud facilitates for obtaining and processing data to build up an on-peak and off-peak timetable to charge electricity storages during off-peak periods. The framework utilized these electricity storages for reduce on-peak electricity occurrences. Their methodology exhibits that the prediction method could join with a transformation technique for assessing delay contemplations.

Conclusion

SGs are developed for solving a number of main issues in the traditional grid such as on-peak load and energy wastage. The IoT paradigm enables connectivity that can help SGs by allowing the grid for monitor and control every operations and devices in the grid. Real-time, reliable, secure, and efficient supplying of electric power in high-quality considers as the key role of the SG in which it represented as the power network combined with various advanced ICTs. Our survey focuses on address the issues of on-peak loads events and Electricity power outages through discussion the development of communication systems especially the Internet of Things applications as well as the integration of Cloud and Fog computing approaches to support SGs and its DR programs. Thus, a number of significant existing research focuses on the IoT applications in SG is briefly overviewed as well as the existing research focus on Cloud and Fog computing approaches that needed for the implementation of IoT-aided SGs projects.

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